

My dances rely on the persistent presence of a question, rendering useless the dependence on memory and anticipation. The rigor is for the dancer to persistently renew his/her questions rather than conform to the dance's guidelines.

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Practices with-in practices: a poemary/bestiary of (non)copyright with-in Contact Improvisation

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Invoking speculations, entities, monsters, and other creatures that crawl from shadows unfolding themselves with-in stories that recall pasts and lost futures to de/un/re/fold presents. Shapeshifting creatures traveling through oral tellings of past events that spark imaginative futurings. In the cracklings of oral transmissions residing within memories, desires, and ... they are never looking for a 'true' recalling of history if that could even exist. Creatures surviving on difference, on imperfection of memory, amnesia. The never one storyline, but the possibility for different recallings is what transforms them and us, making them lively vehicles for haunting past-present-futures.

Winter, cold, gray, Brussels, end of 2021. A book by Anthea Kraut was on our living room table ghostly coloring our conversations. Meldy had bought ‘Choreographing copyright. Race, gender, and intellectual property rights in American dance’ from Anthea Kraut. We started discussing around the ideas that Anthea¹ proposes and thinking them with Contact Improvisation (CI). We remembered that within the oral recites around CI history, there was this particular moment where a decision of non-copyright/non-trademarking CI was made. In these recites, sometimes this decision had been taken by ‘the core-group’², and other times just Steve Paxton was mentioned. Maybe a detail, maybe something that weaves with the history(ies) of CI.

was make --- acted / volition-intention-agency; some words that we’ll leave here to float around this phrase

So, in the boiling of some felt thoughts we started looking for references to try to taste a little bit of what was at play at the moment this small group considered the possibility of trademarking CI and certify teachers. We found a grasp of it in some written institutional discussions: the 1975 Newsletters (where some of the exchanges about the subject are shared), some CQ articles, Cynthia Novack’s book, an interview with Nita Little, and Karen Schaffman’s and Keith Hennessy’s Ph.D. dissertations. For sure, this event is discussed or presented in many other opportunities and formats, but let’s say that for our writings these are the texts we had reached for/encountered³. We had a hunch: we were feeling something in our guts, a discomfort, and we had the feeling it had to do with that. We started pulling the thread with these questions: *If copyright is a creator of value then how does non-copyright perform valorization within CI practices, spaces, discourses? Considering copyright as a neoliberal colonial practice, then what does the valorisation of non-copyright as an important defining moment perform with-in CI? If we think non-trademarking/ non-copyrighting CI resists certain ways of commodifying, why does it seem like it should also prevent hierarchy and privilege?*

1 We are using first names when referencing, as a gesture to circumvent heritages of last names, recognizing that these are people like us with whom we are thinking, and also trying to circumvent the authorization that certain ways of citing generate.

2 A group of dancers who had been involved in the set of performances named ‘Contact Improvisation’ (CI) in John Weber Gallery in New York City in 1972, auto-referenced as the core-group.

3 We realize that all these historical references are from the US. So we are referring mostly to major /established/institutionalized narratives. We acknowledge that other narratives do exist, but we are interested in analyzing ‘major narratives’ that may be then exported.

This then became a (re)search, an iterative moving towards, intending to go nowhere and unfold many-where. A search moved, paused, breathed, collapsed by questions, emotions, emergencies, weather, questions, pulsions, silences, a book, memories, anger, conversations, between Brussels, Oberlin, and Córdoba, desire for something else, desire for movement, rents getting higher, excitement, questions, excitement, living room teas, ... When starting to look for literature, we were thinking of it through the lenses of the poststructuralist theoretical slogan the 'Death of the Author'. As a first impulse, we were driven to go along with the willingness to 'destroy authorship' as such, a pseudo-punk gesture that we were planning from our living room (in cold gray winter, post-covid punches). As we kept on reading-thinking-talking-sharing-feeling-moving (and spring and sun started weaving with these lines), the literalness of the 'Death of the Author' started to flounce away. Our 'corazonada' -hunch from the heart- was telling us that it should not be a matter of author yes/ author no. Even though CI hasn't been copyrighted/trademarked, we believe that the concept-practices associated with these legal procedures still haunt our practices, our gestures, our images-of-thought. So, rather than considering authorship on its own, **we became interested in the practices and heritages of copyright and trademark within (and with-out) the CI-ings, that bound together authorship, originality, ownership, artist-genius/choreographer-as genius, and...value.** We will explore a poemary, a bestiary of the possible entanglements of copyright and CI that we are calling *Practices with-in practices: a poemary/bestiary of (non)copyright with-in CI, -and beyond.*

<...buscar o investigar no es, de ningún modo iluminar. Es una travesía en las sombras, una exposición de contraluces, un correr de velos, un espejismo, una ficción.>/<... searching or researching (investigating) is not, in any way, to illuminate. It is a journey (voyage) through the shadows, an exposure of backlightings (contrasts), a running of veils, a mirage, a fiction.>

(Ileana Diéguez, 2019)

We invite you to go for a balade with the questions and creatures that unfold in the way, and hopefully with your own weavings. 'Non pas devenir plus sensibles [...], mais apprendre à devenir capable d'accorder de l'attention. Accorder prend ici en charge le double sens de 'donner son attention à' et de reconnaître la manière dont d'autres êtres sont porteurs d'attentions...' / 'Not to become more sensitive [...], but to learn to be able to tune attention. Tuning here assumes the double meaning of 'giving attention to' and recognizing the way in which other beings are carriers of attention...' (Despret Vinciane, 2019).

Boiling dinner: word-soup

word-soup: *copyright/trademark, authorship, origin, originality, ownership, property, singular-artist-genius, myth of origin, history....value.*

Although copyright and trademark are different, both practices are highly associated with many other notions. A 'word soup' where, although different, words such as authorship, ownership, property, origin, originality, value, are hauntingly linked. Such reciprocal links among them do not exist a priori, they have emerged and been put together through time and practices; their repetition has greatly contributed to stabilizing the reciprocity between such **concept-practices**: authorship equals origin equals originality equals ownership equals property, equals singular-artist/author-genius, equals myth of origin, equals history....implies and formulates/preserves value...

Of course, as CI, these words have histories as well as relatings; and as CI, they are not a denomination but practices. We consider that authorship, ownership, property, originality, value ..., are not states/characteristics or denominations intrinsic to objects, ideas, movements, dance forms, people...; **authorship, ownership, property, originality, value ... are practices**; they are built through gestures and in their iteration, their repetition, **they build specific ways of relating; they build specific habits; they shape our ability to enable the world, of making-world-with, of world-ing.**

Then, the 'copyright story and decision' in CI works for us as an excuse to explore this word-soup and the practices within CI that create and sustain relations between them.

Copyrighting/trademarking CI: an excuse maybe

There was a proposal to copyright or trademark the name Contact Improvisation in order to “protect the work from dangerous or uninformed activities under its name”. This proposal was rejected at the same time as the small group agreed to start a journal to share CI principles and practices. These decisions had huge implications for the future of CI, allowing it to develop as an open source form, a community based practice, with no central ownership or control, trademark or teacher certification.⁴

(Hennessy Keith, 2017)

Somehow this decision seems like a hinge, like a pivot point in the history of CI. Have you already heard or imagined the question What would have been of CI(s) if copyright or trademark would had been pursued? How would you imagine it?

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After weeks have passed a letter with a court date falls through my mailbox. My breath stops for a moment. I knew it was coming. Many thoughts and what-ifs. Would this have happened if CQ still existed, if I had paid my membership to the CI-organization, if I had done that teacher training, if I ... I remember reading that the decision not to copyright/trademark CI led to the production of CQ. When it disappeared I wondered what would continue ensuring the non-institutionalization of CI. To ensure this desire these concepts need to be reinstated over and over again because the possibility for trademarking/ copyrighting keeps existing.

It's a rainy day when I receive the email. The words are in a legal style. I have difficulty comprehending their reasoning... We demand that you immediately cease the use and distribution of all infringing works derived from the work 'CI falling in images', and all copies, including electronic copies, of same, that you deliver to us, if applicable, all unused, undistributed copies of same, or destroy such copies immediately and that you desist from this or any other infringement of our rights in the future.

⁴ Other possible quote by Hennessy: <The decision in the early 1970s to reject copyrighting or trademarking contact improvisation revealed a trust in more horizontal and open forms of organization and dissemination. This decision was intended to make CI dancing available and accessible to all persons and all bodies, eschewing both institutional permission and virtuosic capabilities....Following improvisational process and the intelligence of the dance itself, early practitioners resisted a suggestion to own the dance and its development by trademarking or copyrighting the name Contact Improvisation.>

*I wonder how this small zine publication around Contact Improvisation caught anyone's attention. It consists of images taken from early CI concerts with commentary written-drawn-cut-and-paste onto them. The email is signed by some attorney and X the executor of **** CI estate. Confusion filled me. After his death, I found myself browsing through those old CQs he had left me as an inheritance. I do remember in the early ones a clear desire not to police the form had been expressed and energy would flow rather to fostering communication between all those doing contact. A decision read through dance history texts as a confirmation of the non-hierarchical, spontaneous, democratic intentions that hallmark the form and its creators. I open the boxes where I have stocked those CQs. A question around the intentionality of this decision pops up. How much of a choice was/is it not to trademark/copyright/police? I opened one and read '...we realized there were already many "non-core" people teaching and doing contact and the job of "recognizing teachers" and enforcing our rules would be very cumbersome.' Had it gotten too big, too spread to get it under control?*

How will I respond? Is someone taking the piss with me? I'm already feeling tired from the effort it will take me to explain myself. Does it require a resurrecting of a historical narrative with an emphasis on non-institutionalization, on collectivity? Or would that just be a revoking of romantic sentiments towards an unstable-ever-changing-never-yet dance practice? Even if copyright was never-yet placed the dancing was thought with-in this possibility, with-in this relating dancing with copyright/trademark.

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Let's call for 1975. In terms of timelines, a frame, a series of consecutive events. Some say CI had been going on already for 3 years when a question around copyright/ trademarking CI started to foreground itself more and more. Of course, this possibility did not bloom out of the blue. As Cynthia Novack suggests the discussions around copyrighting or certifying the form that a small group was having in 1975, and already the possibility of considering that for CI, was very enclosed with how the 'dance world'⁵ was being organized until that moment: <[in the '70's there was an] overwhelming presence of similar institutions in the professional dance world. The organization of the dance world existed as a model for how to cope with the difficulties of self-definition and economic competition, and such institutionalization was proposed as an immediate solution to problems and as a kind of natural evolution of a dance form> (Novack Cynthia, 1990).

⁵ As our text, this reference to the dance world excludes many dances.

Interestingly, and as we believe also more precise, where Cynthia uses the expression ‘a kind of natural evolution’ of a dance form, Susan Leigh Foster specifically refers to a series of ‘transformations of dancing’ usually related to commodifying dance⁶ (Foster Susan Leigh, 2019).

Cynthia continues: in this context the decision not to trademark or certify CI <contrasted with other modern dance choreographers’ overt attempts to protect and control their material>. Read in this line of thought and in a US dance context stamped, shaped and embodied by the practice of valuing big solo artists (such as Cunningham, Graham, ..) that fosters the naturalization of direct links between terms such as ‘choreographer’/‘author’ and ‘ownership’⁷, it does not seem strange that such a decision was and continues to be read as a confirmation of the non-hierarchical, non-institutional, spontaneous, cooperative intentions that hallmark the form; something that has been widely celebrated by CI practitioners, researchers, and many more.

We could start by thinking with *the contrast* that Cynthia mentions. We believe that there is something with this breaking-point image, this pivot image, *the contrast* proposed by Cynthia, that has contributed to building this decision, this event, as an almost revolutionary myth. We believe this condenses a specific interpretation of the events, a method of interpreting and recording history, and of assigning/giving importance. A practice of reading-while-creating history, and of creating/giving value.

How non-copyright takes density within CI? how it co-compose our field of attention? How it compose our narratives and dancing territories?

CI not being copyrighted/trademarked seems to be one of the things that ‘define’ a specific aspect of the form, mostly related to its radicality and how it gets determined through commodifying practices. We notice it in titles of writings such as: *A Radically Unfinished Dance; Displacing Vision: Contact Improvisation, Anarchy, and Empathy; Bodies on the Line: Contact Improvisation*

⁶ Susan Leigh Foster: <Undergirding and enabling the transformation of dancing into monetary value are two fundamental kinds of conversions: first, dance’s substantiality must be further fortified and enhanced so that dance movements become more easily measurable, repeatable and teachable. In this way they can be subjected to strategies for reproducing them more cheaply, quickly and efficiently. With this added materiality, dance can also be modified so as to render it more impressive and desirable. And second, those who are exchanging dance, as teachers, choreographers, and dancers, must learn to disengage or muffle the sensory experience of dancing and one’s experiences of the complexities of physicality during dancing, in order to emphasize mastery.>

⁷ For more on the links between ‘ownership’, ‘author’, ‘choreographer’ and racism, colonialism and gender we suggest you check the work by Anthea Kraut ‘Choreographing Copyright: Race Gender and Intellectual Property Rights in American Dance’, 2016.

and Technique of Nonviolent Protest; Sentir et se Mouvoir Ensemble. Micro-politiques du contact improvisation; Ambivalent Norms, Radical Potential: Contact Improvisation Re-considered; CONTACT vs CAPITALISM.

We are curious, not to question the celebration and the acknowledgment itself, but how this celebration is shaped, with which gestures, and how these gestures shape (and are shaped by) our CI discourses and readings. And in which bigger gestures they are immersed. Therefore, rather than performing a historicization or bringing to light of the events around the non-copyright/trademark decision, **we became interested in the images, assertions, paradoxes, and gestures that certain readings of this event contribute to create, establish, and stabilize.** How these images perform; and how we might perform and re-affirm these images through specific practices. Because *it is not discourses that govern CI spaces but habitus, thinking habits as those corporeal, spatial, in/conscient affects (affections), that become frozen as gestures or repetitive behaviors.*

So, by now you may have the feeling that we have brought to the table this event (the decision to not-trademark CI) not because it interests us as a historical event of a valuable decision per se - which we do acknowledge-, but because there is a certain restlessness that we have been experiencing with how this decision is read (in the mainstream, traditional, institutional spaces), and how specific readings perform and affirm habitus of thinking-doing, of co-creating world, of world-ing. A discomfort, a tension, related to a particular shape the celebration of this non-institutionalization has taken. A celebration that, apart from granting -and creating- value, **brings forward a particular practice of valuing that we find in tension with what it celebrates: a valuation that operates by hierarchization, a valuation that orders legitimacy.** We are interested in *practices of valuing*, rather than value, since value works as a given and can be thought with-in verbs such as give-take-(re)distribute-. Practices of valuing are built on gestures. *<En cada gesto de la vida cotidiana hay una visión del mundo implícita/ In every gesture of daily life there is an implicit worldview-cosmology> (Férrandez-Savater,). <“How does the human body dance the world?” What we want to examine...is the possibility of understanding dance as an incarnation of a civilization’s world view> (David B. Richardson with Sheets-Johnstone, 1984; through (Akinleye Adesola, 2020)).*

Many layers are overlapped in these last paragraphs; a sedimentation of meaning-makings, of practices that consolidate to emerge as a rock, as gestures, as habits, that we carry within and beyond us. *<En cada gesto de la vida cotidiana hay una visión del mundo implícita/ In every*

gesture of daily life there is an implicit worldview-cosmology>, (Fernández-Savater Amador, 2017). We are interested in working/thinking with this sedimentation process. We are here, inviting you to co-create together the threshing of the minerals and grains with-in these rocks, their composition, and -more importantly for us- the way they relate, they conglomerate to be together in this form. Pause. With what memories, practices, movements, beings, is your body sedimented? While saying and breathing through this, we cannot stop thinking the questions with which Susan opens her book 'Valuing Dance: Commodities and Gifts in Motion': *What makes something valuable? How is its value generated and established, then secured and preserved? How is value intimated, legitimated, promulgated, enforced and defended?* Maybe these are the questions that haunt this essay, that haunt the wordings, the tracings that we'll be attempting through these pages.

It seems that there are two rivers, two paths, two questioning, that converge within the text, or perhaps one that is nested inside the other. We are curious about how copyright and trademark practices are integrated into CI, despite it being an "open-source" entity. Additionally, we are interested in exploring the role of non-copyrighting CI in generating value within the CI community, how non-copyright performs CI and its CI-ings.

BEAST: Repetition. Iteration. World-ing tendencies and intensities

Repetition ← → as stabilizing ← → naturalization ← → instauration

Repetition ← → as tuning attention ← → as reshaping perception

Repetition ← → bodies in the making ← → as our ability to enable the world

We prefer repetition/iteration rather than embodied, because we are interested, not in the individuality, in the personal on its own, but to think repetition as that that stabilizes the embodiment of practices of relating and valuing in a bigger corpus that we are (people, newsletters, writings, festivals, kissings, gossips, dancefloors, cats, mountains, ai...).

We choose to stay with repetition since it works in many layers. Repetition works somatically, not as something that gets glued to our flesh, our corpus, or the bigger corpus that we are. But as something that reshapes what our bodies and our corpora are becoming in relating. Agency [and attention] is an enactment, not something that someone or something has. Through repetition of gestures, we nurture certain tunings of attention, reshape perception and sensorial fields, while being (re)shaped by them. Topologies that arise as and through phenomena. Perceiving the world we are-with as ontologically unchanging, is also related to repetition (and repetition of attention-ings). We assemble territory through gestures, as we are that territorialized. Moreover, repetition and habits escape <at once the purely determined and the pure reflexivity of free will> (Bardet Marie and Ginot Isabelle, winter 2012, reprinted on 2019) as it also escapes the personal/individual but they are not merely collectively ‘corporal’; they also escape the human. Gestures/practices have their own agency; they transform (and are transformed by the historicity of) our textures, contrasts, surfaces, fleshes, backgrounds, and how we relate with-in the world; it transforms the bigger corpus that we are. Certain gestures are carriers of attention, they carry more weight and catch more light. Some have more attention-gravity than others. Some gestures make that bigger for some other gestures. We transform them and are transformed by them, they change our ability to enable the world. We wonder, *how is our field of attention transformed, (re)configure? How is attention mobilized, what mobilizes attention?* And we repeat, <*the world that I and other dancers are together exploring is inseparable from the world we are together creating*> ((Sheets-Johnstone, 2009) through ((Akinleye Adesola, 2020))).

Structure (and 'power structures/dynamics', hierarchies, legitimacy, colonialism...) does not represent an external set of relations, but structures are themselves produced in iteration of practices, and as part of the world we/our bodies/subjectivity/(...) are (re)configured within those iterations. *<Humans are intra-actively (re) constituted as part of the world's becoming. Which is not to say that humans are the mere effect, but neither are they/we the sole cause, of the world's becoming. The particular configuration that an apparatus takes is not an arbitrary construction of our choosing; nor is it the result of causally deterministic power structures.>* (Barad Karen, 2007) Structures then, could be thought together with what Karen Barad calls apparatuses, *<apparatuses are phenomena, material configurings/reconfigurings, that are produced and reworked through a dynamics of iterative intra-activity. This dynamics entails a rethinking of the nature of causality and the roles of exclusions in creating the conditions of possibility for contesting and iteratively remaking apparatuses>*. Attention could be also thought together with apparatuses, as potential fields of attention-ings, is (are, because there is never one) iteratively (re)configured. Attention fields shape and are shaped by attention tendencies and intensities, that are always (re)configured, weaved, entangled with memories, spatial fields, temporalities, weather, stories, cars, practices / repetitions / gestures.

word-soup: *copyright/trademark, authorship, origin, originality, ownership, property, singular-artist-genius, myth of origin, history....value.*

How is this word-soup iteratively put together? Through and with which practices? How does this word-soup sustain the iteration of such practices within CI? How it (re)configures our field of attention? Our fields of importances? Our flesh, textures, densities, ghosts, fluids? How our gravitational-field is affected and affects?

World-ing is not only a matter of perception, world-ing is also a matter of matter-ings, of flesh, of sedimentations, of electrons, of fluids.

<Matter is a dynamic intra-active becoming that is implicated and enfolded in its iterative becoming. Matter(ing) is a dynamic articulation of configuration of the world. [...] The iterative enfolding of specific materializing phenomena into practices of materialization matters to the specifics of the materialization it produces. In short, the iterative enfolding of matter comes to matter. Matter is the sedimenting historicity of practices/agencies and an agentive force in the

world's differential becoming. Becoming is not an unfolding in time but the inexhaustible dynamism of the enfolding of mattering>. (Barad Karen, 2007)

BEAST: Settling and defining. *Determinability*. (Separability, determinability, and sequentiality principles).

Copyright is a legislative practice and legislation works through the idea of fixing-settling-establishing-determining something, like rights. The habitus of thinking-being-becoming through the iteration of legislation works with the hope that something gets (finally) fixed, settled, determined, granted for good. This sense of determination resists possibilities of tuning our attention with something else, and becoming something else with other ways of moving-thinking-doing, of being changed. Even if a copyright/trademark was never-yet placed the dancing was thought with-in this possibility, with-in this relating dance with copyright/trademark. What was meant to be fixed and didn't get fixed? What has been fixed through an idea of legacy? Imagining that non-copyright settles anything is a practice greatly entangled with the determinate and defining that copyright asks for.

If copyright is a creator of value then how does non-copyright perform valorization within CI practices, spaces, discourses? Considering copyright as a neoliberal practice, then what does the valorization of non-copyright as an important defining moment perform with-in CI?

If we think non-trademarking/ non-copyrighting CI resists certain ways of commodifying (but not all!), why does it seem like it should also prevent hierarchy and privilege?

We wondered what questions have no currency in this settledness/settlement. When thinking CI through non-copyright/ non-trademark, what are the questions that cannot be addressed? We have experienced that questions around value and questions around money are particularly left behind. It would seem that by saying it hasn't been copyrighted/trademarked it avoided being commodified for good. Since it is thought of mainly as an 'open-to-everyone, collective practice', where

‘everyone can become a teacher without certification’, it would seem that we forget that work is involved and that money exists within our practice. It acts as an obliteration process, erasing from our fields of attention experiences related to this, and questions that can be posed. Then it is hard to talk about the ‘helpers’ role in festivals as working bodies (usually underprivileged), that end up sustaining that practitioners who can have different access to time and money can be part of festivals as just attendees (please, be aware that attendees that ‘help’ or ‘volunteer’ for a couple of tasks does not in any way revert this). How does this affect and is affected through encounters on the dancefloor? And we repeat, considering copyright as a neoliberal practice, then what does the valorization of non-copyright as an important defining moment perform with-in CI? If we think non-trademarking/ non-copyrighting CI resists certain ways of commodifying (but not all!), why does it seem like it should also prevent hierarchy and privilege?

The matter is that determination and settling are not only configured through copyright. Separability, determination, and sequencing are three onto-epistemological pillars on which rational modernity is based (Ferreira da Silva Denise, 2019). And non/copyright exists with them and through them. Which practices (and presuppositions) within CI, entangled with the non-copyright material-discursivity, contribute to (re)produce and repeat these pillars, and are (re)configured by them?

BEAST: author-genius / legitimization

word-soup: *copyright/trademark, authorship, origin, originality, ownership, property, singular-artist-genius, myth of origin, history....value.*

This tension that we experience on the fibers that iteratively co-compose CI has already been shared by Karen Schaffman. In her PhD dissertation, Karen takes a series of gestures that took place during the 25th Anniversary Celebration of CI in June 1997 (Jubilee- CI 25) to pose a question to the (pre)assumed anti-hierarchical principles/values of the form -something we'll not discuss in these pages-. She considers gestures around 'Steve's Fireside Chat'⁸:

The only Talk Structure held outside the schedule of the daytime activities was "Steve's Fireside Chat" which instead got an evening of its own. Granting Paxton this special moment read like a testimonial, paradoxically affirming his authority in the antihierarchical contact improvisation community.

Granting Paxton a special evening with an honorary chair the community instills his authority. With such illustrious status, the notion of horizontality certainly comes into query and stirs the dilemma concerning the inheritance of white male artistic privilege by illuminating remnants of modernist genius. It is relevant to notice the paradox of his position as well as the complexity of antihierarchical politics. (Schaffman Karen, 2001)

Her questioning emerges within many other events/occasions during the Jubilee also described in her text which weave as well many experiences of horizontality with-in CI⁹. 'Experiences of

8 Steve's Fireside Chat' a special evening event dedicated to him within the Jubilee of CI25.

9 Examples: <Everyone stated their name and where they were from. It was a long democratic process, but each person present was seen and heard.[...] Space would be available for rehearsals and bodywork, new classes could be added, small group discussions were not fully formulated, and plenty of volunteers were still necessary. The reference room remained open day and evening and there was an ongoing space for jamming (informal, or "come as you are," dancing)[..] A Teacher's Idea Log invited contact improvisation teachers to share scores, exercises, and structures. [...] Birthday Presence : Nina Martin wrote "\$200 Bucks," where she considers the politics of anti institutionalization. Martin declared "I own the form, I am the form. How many other systems can give that?" Martin expressed her appreciation that she "didn't teach 'Paxton technique'" and how she "was able to explore and develop her interests in the form without a board of supervisors passing judgment and deciding if [she] was indeed teaching Contact."> (Schaffman Karen, 2001)

horizontalities' are of course not universal; who experiences horizontality and when is a big topic to dive into that still has many threads from which to pull¹⁰. If we take the focus from the question if CI 'is' actually antihierarchical, we read that Karen certainly calls for what we believe is a mechanism that still surfaces today: the practice of privileging space and time -more commonly to white cis hetero men-, in this case formatted as a talk (unidirectional), to a single recognized person. In a certain way, this particular privileging of time and space (more precisely how time and space are composed, which includes audience predisposition/memory), serves to feed the continuous granting of single-prevalent authorship and the Romantic conceptions of the author as genius (the artist-genius). For now, let's stay a little bit with this gesture, this privileging space and time. Take a moment, can you associate this gesture with other gestures, other moments, events, other sayings? (With)in or (with)out CI?

The three-act structure. Scene: (first act: set up) <a fake cardboard fireplace and an oversized pleather easy chair>; practitioners sitting around facing the scene waiting for the speech/conversation. (second act: rising action, climax) Steve enters the room, avoiding the chair. Steve walks around amongst the sat practitioners, talking while moving. People turning to be able to see him. An emptied chair. (Third act: resolution) Steve brings back the power to the people: *'..in a way for the last twenty five years that chair has been empty because at the beginning it was clear that although I was organizing material and other people were learning material, that the material itself, the contact between two people, which was the subject of this, was going to be invented in partnership...! have many times been wished "happy birthday" here, as though this was special to me...I would just like to wish you all "happy birthday" because it is a partnership that makes this happen...'*. Nodding heads. General applause. End scene. How is the piece called? (: <Circumventing the Throne> Karen called it. Love it!)

But there is more to it than just a narrative. What calls our attention is how we just keep on creating the conditions for Steve to redeem himself, to 'teach' us something, and for us to 'learn' from him, even though that might not be his intention. It has to do with setting an honorary chair and not. It has to do with the silences we do, how we nod and when, the questions that we pose, and those that fade away behind our smiles. How through our gestures, through the practices that we are with, we

10 There is with-in CI a very common gesture, in this case, considering 'the values of the form' as something that would pre-establish/ pre-grant 'forever' (foreground) horizontality, equalness, openness. Almost just because we are naming a desire for horizontality, equalness, openness. Not to mention that these values are usually understood as 'universally perceptible', directly eliminating all possibilities of discordance, different existences, and dialogue. As if practices wouldn't be constantly reshaping and reshaped by CI. More on 'experiences of horizontality' in Keith dissertation.

give him (or others) the possibility to surf such situations and generate disorientation. We create our fictional heroes through our fictional narrative gestures. The snake that eats its own tale.

It seems paradoxical to value the decision of non-trademarking CI while simultaneously performing a particular *practice of valuing* that resurrects Steve as a singular author-genius-artist, that although not necessarily intentional, has granted great moral value and recognition to Steve who was considered as 'the choreographer who collectivized his work'. Adding a layer to this, this three-act structure (greatly used in Hollywood) is a specific way of relating with events, talks about a particular way of becoming with and of worlding (creating worlds), of enabling the world. We are not at all intending to generalize, and say that this exact gesture is constantly repeated in every context. We are mostly interested in opening space and letting air in the corpora-that-we-are, to let questions in our practices, maybe to notice some slightly different gestures that could perform similarly. Maybe it makes you remember other gestures that also contribute to a specific co-composing world. We understand that this example represents a cliché already: a particular spatial distribution, a center (the front/a facing towards), the unidirectional speech; it already tastes outdated. Certainly, nowadays this specific spatial distribution is not present in CI-spaces, but the attentional distribution does -and it might not have to do with the presence of Paxton per se. Distribution in space (-time) may change; there might be a circle, there may be more people, we might call it a conversation, a lab,... but that's not just enough. We are not just referring to a particular spatial (temporal) composition. Still through certain gestures, certain invitations to relating, the emergent field of attention (which refers to our perception, but also to our ontological becomings, to what we are with) may iteratively arise with the same weighted-centering. How through and with our gestures we iteratively co-compose the tissue of our attention gravitational-field? our senso-space-time-mattering? How do we contribute to setting the conditions for the emergence of a black hole, a center of attention, in this case a Paxton-black-hole, towards which light and attention bend and get called and sucked? How do attention and value co-compose each other? How do they contribute to composing space-time? How legitimacy arises?

What we are trying to think with is more subtle than just proposing sitting in a circle and saying out loud that everyone can talk/give their opinion, our practices <have effects on the legitimacy of ways of doing, of granting and taking authorizations-authorities from voices, of the political practices and what we understand as political in our practices> (Bardet Marie, 2021). They will allow for something different than having a person (or people) on a stage / a privilege spot, but that will not imply that everyone will be considered, nor have actually access to share their experiences, thoughts or even questions. If our field of attention, of importances, are already tuned to given importances

how is it possible for other ways to emerge? How is it possible for other questionings to emerge? How does this affect our improvisations? Maybe we need to start asking different questions, questions that do not set always the same people as possible, and sometimes the only, repliers of them; that do not mobilize the flow of attention in the same way as always. And asking questions does not always have to do with words, but with sensing the guts, the intestines, the ass, the sounds, ...

And we repeat the chorus: *How is value generated and established, then secured and preserved? How is value intimated, legitimated, promulgated, enforced and defended? To whom or to what does this value serve?*

BEAST: origin - linear time - history -author -owner.

Sequentiality.

Legal structures for creative copyright/trademark have served the idea of where 'it' originates from, and to whom 'it' belongs. To some extent, the question of who is entitled to take such a decision (copyrighting, trademarking, certifying, etc.) or even consider the possibility of taking it is linked to this. For CI, could that person be us? You? Who are you thinking of? Was this clear already for you before we put these questions here? Somehow to pose these questions doesn't seem so weird, so out of context. What is it that supports them? What do they move forward?

Keith Hennessy shares an experience in CI36 'Founder's Talk' a panel discussion that he was facilitating: *<A near obsessive retelling of the creation myth of CI as a series of personal anecdotes by the surviving (still teaching) founders inappropriately distracts from the many persons, contexts, and formal evolutions of contact improvisation.>¹¹* (Hennessy Keith, 2017)

By recalling this event, Keith tries to bring our attention to the insistence on reading history as a linear causal effect that always needs an origin (a center) from which to exist: the origin myth. To

11 *<The history of CI would be better told as a history of love affairs, of dancers touching each other, experimenting, yielding to each other, resisting each other.>* (Hennessy Keith, 2017)

some extent this (other) gesture seems (also) like the snake that eats its own tale: thinking of history linearly, looking for an origin, justifies the need and value for a Founder's Talk that simultaneously asks for an articulation of events in a particular linear way. What can(not) emerge, can(not) exist within this loop? Why does it seem that all CI moments, expansions, diversion, are causally/sequentially linked to such origin? At the core of the conceptions of original expression, and therefore of the artist-genius, lies the idea that ideas belong to their creators because ideas are manifestations of their creator's personality or self (and the presupposition of a self-determined subject). Keith accurately describes a consequence of this gesture: < [a distraction] from the many persons, contexts, and formal evolutions of contact improvisation>. A distraction from other movements, other relatings that have shaped and still co-shape CI.

What constitutes [has constituted and (re)configures] CI is not what's only happening in an institutional frame: jams, festival programs, classes, in CQ, in our duo, [in academic writing on CI]. Although around these spaces/ practices is where major narratives are constructed, simultaneously there are minor events that are boiling and affect and are being affected with major narratives. We are interested in all collective practices that emerge outside the curricula: we would put our attention towards what happens around the kitchen-space[...], what happens outside the jam during the jam, autogestion of helpers-labs during the teachers-meeting,... (Ijpelaar M., Campise F., 2019/2022)

The artist-genius, the origin, the legacy, and even a particular way of celebrating a decision, are specific operations that only allow a particular kind of history (often related to 'what actually happened', what can be named, and what can be recalled). It makes us think about the zombie-images that Amador Fernández-Savater refers to. The artist-genius, the origin (that also has a kind of mystical, sacred taste to it) may work as zombie-images, and by that they <weaken effective practices and living experiences by giving value only to certain aspects of them to the detriment of others: the massive is privileged, the moments of open insurrection, the epic, the hyper-visible, etc.>. There is something in the practice of asking Paxton, the core group, the archives, what is of matter, what is of importance, what is valuable, what is/was there, that silences and homogenizes not only what is (was/will be) of importance for the practitioners, but also the pallet of importances that could emerge with-in and around CI. There is an archive of videos (fall after newton, performances, interviews) widely shared to access the 'origins' of CI, the 'pure' form... Copyright law's prerequisite that a work be "fixed in any tangible medium of expression" is not far from our practices that intend to understand, and access, what the 'form is'. Like copyright, they may work

with the definition and fixation of forms, of ideas; they demand a particular way of asking questions to a research process that found itself CI-ing. Of course, there is no problem in having an archive, but it is our relating with archive and archiving that we are finding ourselves uncomfortable with. What do we archive? What does it resemble? What questions do we ask when engaging with the archive? Some of these relatings have a close resemblance to copyright-practices. <The lack of physical boundaries surrounding intellectual property is in fact what gave rise to the fixity and tangibility requirements of copyright law. The irony for dance is that copyright, with its requirement that works be “fixed in a tangible medium of expression,” has represented the temporal solidity—the past and the future—which it supposedly lacks>. Some of our practices of valuing are concerned with what it (CI) should be and it looks for an answer in ‘the’ origin. Such practices are nothing more than an apparatus of capture. What does it imply for an improvisational and research practice -research improvisational practice? How does this work with our imagery of CI? How does this co-compose our attention while dancing-moving, organizing events, writing about CI,...?

BEAST: historical archaeological artifact

12

Photo taken during the exhibition ‘Collective Gestures’ at CI@50 critical mass 2022 (Oberlin College, US). Description: The photo shows the description of a letter inside a glass showcase. The description reads ‘Contact Copyright papers: copyright notice written to John Gamble, September 22nd, 1975. A copyright notice written to John Gamble stating that he is unauthorized to teach contact due to lack of experience and is not permitted to use the name Contact Improvisation in advertisements of his workshops and classes. Out of the original six practitioners listed, only Curt Sidall and Nita Little signed.’ Pasted on top of the glass showcase there is a typed statement: ‘This was a draft of a private letter to John Gamble which was never sent. It was published without consent. The description below is an inaccurate interpretation and a false narrative of actual events without the context’ signed by Curt Sidall and Nita Little. A friction in history.

This letter doesn’t appear for the first time at this exhibition. It had already been published by Nancy Stark Smith in CQ Vol.23 No.1 Winter-Spring 1998. What we want to look at here is how

12 Waiting for permission to share the photo here. But you can picture it.

this letter that got published and was signed by certain someones and not signed by certain others (a.o. Steve and Nancy) creates specific narratives of valuing some over others through an opposition. Some strains from which to gossip. By having the signatures of Nita and Curt appear in the publication of this letter, it seems as if they were pro-copyright and the others not. As if a minority-majority voting happened and it's thanks to those 4 others that CI appears as an open-source practice. The choice for non-copyright gives specific valorizations within CI that might be less granted to Nita and Curt since they signed this letter.

In every gesture on 'showing'/bringing to light/... a 'factual' event in history, there are choices being taken/made, a creation. Do those signatures represent that? The corruption of objects, the collection/collector, the historical archaeological artifact that operates colonization by extracting pieces from events and relating and creating history. You may find another letter signed by everyone that might say something different, or the same letter signed by no one.

Chorus: What makes something valuable?

How is its value generated and established, then secured and preserved?

How is value intimated, legitimated, promulgated, enforced and defended?

History -causal, chronological, even intentional-, and practices around historizing, create and are created by a certain type of attention; they co-opt particular modes of attention. Modes of attention-ing do not have to do with light. val flores proposes us to go/think even beyond this (in)visibility dyad: *<I invite us to collectively think of the regimes of light [-the visible/visibility-] as modes of production of knowledge and normality that cause their own ignorance, because rather than hide, what they do is naturalize and inhibit certain possibilities of vision, perception, [attention], perception and interpretation of bodies, which is neither more nor less than our ability to enable the world>* (flores val, 2021). Given this, *<how is it that these habits, these gestures, condition our dreams and political experiences?>* (flores val, 2021).

Other practices around memory need to be considered that implement a certain mode of attention that brings out differences rather than contributing to homogenizing our memories and thus our dances with-in memories. Practices of observing that multiply territories with-in CI. In this sense, we repeat *this is not a fight for visibility*. It is not one truth for another. As Vinciane Despret

suggests, not <other hypotheses, other perspectives, but other territories, other ways of living, and therefore of making world>.

BEAST: heritage – legacy- lineage

And then, how is value inherited? What are the practices of inheriting value in CI? How is lineage created? How is lineage inherited through generations? What practices sustain lineage? How close to the source can I get? Who can access and who cannot? Who benefits from this lineage? Who has the time and money to invest in festivals, workshops,? How does this sum towards the commodification of CI? What has been fixed through an idea of legacy? A corpus of value?

BEAST: Contrast – difference. *Separability*. Value through hierarchization

We are in a crack. Maybe too much information. But we are layering; our method lies in layering. We breathe. We would like to bring attention to the edges of the perceptible. Perception as that which is not linked with ‘the natural’, but as what emerges with gestures, habits, memories, actions, relatings, and an excess that cannot be grasped. We breathe before continuing.

We bring back the *contrast*, the *pivot image*, proposed by Cynthia. The revolutionary myth.

Chorus: What makes something valuable?

How is its value generated and established, then secured and preserved?

Marie Bardet shares her urgency to bring back, to remember¹³ something she encounters within her practices and collective sharings, what would seem to be a gesture of dualism. She suggests that the dualist gesture <is carried out through a concatenation of three different operations: differentiate, oppose, hierarchize, in the blink of an eye> (Bardet Marie, 2021). Three different operations that are wrapped <in a single gesture [...]; establish a point-by-point opposition (everything that is A is not B, everything that is B is not A) to define each of the elements; and value these elements among themselves, hierarchizing them>. A single(d) -as in made single- gesture that would seem to emerge naturally in our habits of thinking (-doing-being).

In the readings of dance history, this gesture appears many times. Sally Banes shares :

<Since the modern dance was predicated so heavily on personal, often intimate, formats, on subjective content, and on individual quests for movement styles that would express not only the physicality of the choreographer, but also his or her thematic concerns and theories of movements, very slight shift in technique or theory from teacher to student came to mean not further refinement but further revolt. The history of modern dance is rapidly cyclical: revolution and institution; revolution and institution.> (Banes Sally, 1987)

We would rather say that it is not so much that <the history of modern dance is rapidly cyclical> (revolution and institution), but that it is rapidly read as cyclical in this way. It is (not) cyclical and it's made cyclical at the same time; a quantic being. Opposing revolution and institution, A and B, differentiating and distinguishing, A is not B. Cutting the relatings among them, detaching one from another, determining/settling/defining them.

Similarly, when reading <the heritage of modern dance> in CI, Cynthia says: *In America, modern dance took on the character of continuing revolution, a re-creation of the American frontier standing counter to the European, aristocratic form of ballet. During the 1930s, John Martin, one of the critical spokesmen for the new modern dance, proclaimed the revolutionary ideology of this undertaking: "It [(the modern dance)] has thrown aside everything that has gone before and started all over again from the beginning". Martin's claim that modern dance threw aside "everything" that had gone before and started all over again "from the beginning" echoes the enduring theme of the new frontier in American history.* (Novack Cynthia, 1990)

13 As Marie shares: Remember as in re-member- Make a member again, make it part of our bodies again, in some particular way. Like knitting it to our members with a particular point of knitting.

It is not strange to read in the former quotes the use of the word ‘revolution’. In Marxist terms, revolution is something that would instaurate/establish something completely new, something different, something that once it arrives is ascertained. But Marx is now far from us, water has flooded the bridge the city our post-capitalist dreams. The famous cut and clean mechanism, as we have also (hopefully) learned from our Covid experiences with the ‘back to normal’ promises, is not as simple as that, are constructions that just serve some, and work as mechanisms of forgetting, mechanism of distraction, and at the same time as mechanisms of valuing.

Marie continues: *this dualist gesture <will have strong consequences -or even stronger- over western thinking as that of the body/mind dualism: repeating this continuously will lead to the naturalization of the fact that any verification of difference is necessarily accompanied by a defining (and definitive) binary opposition, and by **a valuation that operates intrinsically by hierarchization**>.*

And we recall Cynthia’s mention of contrast. It is not that contrast is a mirage, it’s not that the pivot image around the decision of non-trademarking/copyrighting CI is a mirage; it’s more what we do with it: <differentiate, oppose, hierarchize, in the blink of an eye>. The contrast as Cynthia articulates it, between CI -not being trademarked/copyrighted- and other dance practices, presents an articulation that talks of opposition. It is not strange that we then encounter CI told within a revolutionary myth narration. The revolutionary image of change. And we recall: CI’s revolutionary myth that seems to be embedded in many CI discourses, particularly in academic and institutional writings. The revolutionary approach towards touch, towards research, towards improvisation, towards its anarchic characteristics, towards attention, is the new commodification and universalization of CI, and it serves as well many of the publicities towards CI. And a whisper resonates spiraling in our ears: <and how CI dancers’ assumptions about the higher value of CI’s code of touch (over all others) mirrors colonial or supremacist practices that many people resist, especially queers and people of color> (Hennessy J. Keith, 2017). To universalize experience mirrors colonial and supremacist practices¹⁴. If copyright is a creator of value then how does non-copyright perform valorization within CI practices, spaces, discourses? As Amador suggests <the revolutionary image of change is determined by a cut, a radical discontinuity between the old and the new. [...] It consists in the overthrow of the old order and in a new beginning, an absolute

14 For a further expansion on this, we refer you to Keith’s work (dissertation); as an opening gate, please consider Akinleye, A.’s essay ‘Contacting Improvising: recognizing institutional racism in our dance classrooms’.

beginning>, determined completely separate from the 'old' order (Separability and Determinability Principles). An origin gets established. All this being crossed by Hegelian philosophy (dialectics, negation, overcoming), that allows to sustain and resolve this apparent paradox of an absolute and at the same time absolutely necessary change (the idea of 'historical necessity' that Hanna Arendt <detects in the metaphors within revolutionary discourses>) (Férrnandez-Savater Amador, 2020). Again, the question here is not if CI (also touch / improvisation / even queerness ...) was/is or not revolutionary, but how this approach to analyzing- thinking-doing are specific ways of valuing and determining CI as 'something on its own': valuing through hierarchization. How do leaders/authority figures of this non-institutionalizing revolution emerge? What do these revolutionary myths serve? Gossips of other dancers that say that CI practitioners have a cult practice towards CI, wink wink.

How can we nurture and let emerge images of difference without separability?

BEAST: volition

was made --- acted / volition-intention-agency

Let's question the volition-intention-agency triad is at the core of the conceptions of singular-author/artist-genius and original expression. It would seem that the ghosts of the Romantic conceptions of the choreographer-artist-genius still h(a)unt us. Original expression, originality, the creation, the origin, are also fed by such triad. When tracing the histories of copyright and its relating to other concepts-practices, Anthea summons Saint-Amour: <original expression was consecrated by the Romantic cult of the individual genius, and that legacy of Romanticism ... has proven both durable and adaptable> (Kraut Anthea, 2016).

I open the boxes where I have stocked those CQs. A question around the intentionality of this decision pops up. How much of a choice was/is it not to trademark/copyright/police? I opened one and read '...we realized there were already many "non-core" people teaching and doing contact

and the job of “recognizing teachers” and enforcing our rules would be very cumbersome’(the small group, 1975). Had it gotten too big, too spread to get it under control?

There is a choice in reading decisions as something we make out of will rather than understanding that they can emerge and accompany them as the ‘core-group’ did. Unlike will, sensitivity does not seek control, but a greater receptivity: an openness, availability, and attention to the world(-ing) we are of and with, as CI is of and with.

7th of June 2022, 20h37 CEST: we just received the news of a new origin possibility

DIGESTING: a collage of other’s wor(l)ds through us – a wish for an incantation that frees the potentials captured by its institutionalized form

How can we play with attention? with disorientation of importances? With other somatic disruptions?

<History creates a certain type of attention, wherever it co-opts particular modes of attention. [...] To deterritorialize is to undo one arrangement, but to reterritorialize on another. It's undoing a way of being territorialized by branching out into other agencements, to reterritorialize according to them. To hesitate. Disagree to find other agreements. To fork out when the going is tough. Ally with powers. To give facts a power that we don't have and that we must learn to build with them: the power to perform, to have unexpected effects and impacts.> (Despret Vinciane, 2019)

<001. We would like to start by putting an interval in the visibility domain. We would like to start by drawing a cartography that does not depend on the idea of location [neither spatially nor

temporally]. We would like to start by proposing an undisciplined and fugitive compositional practice. We would like to begin by thinking about the destruction of the world as we know it as a form of care. We would like to start with the decolonization of colonized matter. We would like to start by cutting with a sword the world of the wound [world-wound]. We would like to begin with a convulsion in grammar. We would like to start with an accident in perception. > Jota Mombaça and Musa Michelle Mattiuzzi in (Ferreira da Silva Denise, 2019)

We want to break a wall in this conglomeration of practices and smell another sea. We are with a sense of exhaustion, a crack in between ruins of futures that never materialize. The non-copyright event, this open-source promise, the revolutionary myth. In our melancholic dwellings, we notice a desire that is looking backward and gets attached to certain strains of past narratives. How the promises of non-trademark/non-copyright, through specific practices, contribute to institutionalizing memories, histories, dances. In our attachments we romanticize certain aspects over others, we give value to specific past narratives and specific ways of building narratives that also become authorities, grant specific authorizations and legitimate specific ways of doing. The romantic attachment to these events are related to their futuring promises in a present tense. What we sense is an exhaustion (of resources) and a change in our fields of importances. Our intendings through these lines are not a questioning of the singular artist itself nor recognition. This is starting to disappear as a question as such. We sense the tension of its vanishing and a pulsión to make it stay. There are practices that are bringing this back, which will haunt our new questions and desires. Some of these practices are what we are trying to bring to the table.

When writing about this we are not referring to redistributing value, it's not about taking value from Steve or other consecrated names, for example, and redistributing it to 'the margins' (queer, practitioners, BIPOC, relatings and and and). It's not about rendering CI more 'inclusive'. Nor to 'bring the invisible (invisibilized) to light'. As Jota and Musa Michelle share <125. *Visibility is a trap and representation is a dead end*> (Ferreira da Silva Denise, 2019). This is not a fight for visibility, to make the ungraspable graspable. In a conversation with Joe Dumit, Joe poses the question Was it ever ungraspable? There is a continual work of resistance going on. We see it and don't want to acknowledge it is visible, actually sensible. That 'culture' is actively resisting things. We consider this resisting as a mechanism that immediately defends a status quo, as a habit of doing. This mechanism contributes to actively 'keeping poor people poor', actively 'looking and giving authorization, legitimizing the same people'. It's very consciously doing it, even if people

who are participating aren't acknowledging that that is what they are doing. The way it is not acknowledged is visible. What we believe, and what we sense, is that this particular way of relating to value-ing and the gestures we have created around valorization are worn out and they exclude. The practices that we shared are mechanisms of 'distraction', of circumvention, they support and sustain the very fabric of privilege, legitimization, and oppression. They exclude memories, questions, beings by bringing us over and over to the same questions and relating. This is neither about utopic dreamings; we are not interested in prebuilding new imaginaries for the future. This is how we would like to be with the new-made-slogan 'staying with the trouble'; doing, thinking and creating from and within/without the discomfort. Can we stay and rest with such discomfort? What habits surface just to resist it? To distract us from what we are sensing?

At this point, there is an image that appears, that pops into our conversations. It's interesting how it (re)appears to us, in this momentum around a 50th anniversary; is it like a vehicle? A resonance made present. We start thinking together with Ishmael Houston Jones and Fred Holland's performance-manifesto "Wrong", <a re-radicalizing of the Contact trope> on the tenth anniversary of Contact Improvisation (1983). As Ishmael describes: <The first wrong thing in our manifesto was that we were Black, and that we'd used a loud sound score, and we wore boots, and clothes, and we talked and we stayed out of physical contact as much as possible. It was a re-radicalizing of the Contact trope> (Houston-Jones Ishmael and Hennessy Keith, 2017). Using (re-)radicalizing as a process that situates with-in other processes, events, stories, rather than thinking that the core self of a dance form, of a practice is radical per se.

And another memory knocks at our door, calling for our attention. A memory, something that stays with-in us, a carrier of attention with which we are tuning. Colectivo EPIICO¹⁵'s manifesto and what this sharing moved. During Oberlin's CI@50 panel discussion called 'Global and Local: Facilitating Contact in Different Communities' Colectivo EPIICO read a manifesto they wrote for that occasion. It was referring to colonial practices and structurings that are and were very sensible and stayed unaddressed during the festival, but still are reproduced in many CI spaces-events. They had been expected to perform what the 'global south' is supposed to perform when included in CI contexts in and of the 'Global North': a sharing of their experience in Mexico and an acknowledgment of the possibility of being able to be in the US ('a triumph'). Instead, the manifesto manifested in the space as a cutting through the 'equality' fabric that protects the CI

15 Colectivo EPIICO: <https://contactquarterly.com/contact-improvisation/newsletter/index.php#view=the-seed-has-been-planted>

furniture from dust; sensed as a collective suspension of breathing. Some things moved, and we cannot arrive at naming them, pinning them down because we don't know and we don't desire to lay in it. Fuimos con-movidas.

How can we play with attention? with disorientation of importances? Disturbios somáticos. Two gestures. A radicalization that does not produce a cut and clean, but that works as resonances as overlappings. Gestures that allow for a glimpse of (re)making, (re)building, (re)imaging CI (as such). They don't create the radical as utopian, the radical potential is sensed for a moment, and it works with what is there. A crack is created, paralyzing for a moment the mechanisms of distraction, disorientating fields of attention, fields of importances. A crack that makes an escape possible, que hacen la fuga posible. Could we pause within this crack? Resting with that which opened, which cracked us and space/time? An opportunity, a possibility, a potential for variability, the possibility of varying the movement as it unfolds¹⁶, the possibility of varying the habit as it unfolds. To have the courage to pool from that other thread, not forcing it to fit our 'determined' beings, practices, and discourses¹⁷. Not to <minimize others' experiences in order to keep your own memories, or sense of self, intact (I have to minimize her wounds because that is what I have done to my own wounds; or I have to minimize her wounds because if I don't I have to change my own history and how I contextualize myself). This personal work is about having the courage to be incomplete, in process> (Akinleye Adesola, 2020). As if 'other's wounds' existed beyond and apart, separate from us. We need the courage to lose things and drop out, desert, colonial practices that iteratively (re)create the bigger corpus that we are with. It asks and requires us to lose something from us, and that may hurt. It asks from us an escape, a desertion of a place, a space of recognition, of automatized gestures, that circumvent what is boiling in the present. A crack that invites us to flee from already-made relatings, narratives, dances. Desert to take the value from it, desert to not support that value. <Desertion asks questions to a world that always already has all the answers. [...] It interrupts the automatisms that we candorously call> "my practice / history / CI / ..." <We desert to be able to think, we think to be able to breathe. [...] a way to keep asking questions. Not

16 Relating it with Reversibility in Feldenkrais as though with Marie Bardet, Isabelle Ginot, and through them with Alan Questel ('Balance' in Feldenkrais Journal, no.24 forthcoming 2012).

17 <It can feel as if we are in a beautiful world working relatively well, and then it is brought to your attention that something bad happened in that beautiful world. We then work to get things back to that same beautiful world before you noticed the bad thing happened. But at its root what that bad thing happening is underlining, is that the world you thought you were in never existed. Trying to get back to the model before the bad thing happened is trying to get back to a fiction (that never existed in the first place). Privilege is when you believe 'we just need to get back to the beautiful world' and you find it hard to believe we can't just find a way to get back there. Becoming aware of privilege involves the frightening concept that if the beautiful world never really existed, then we do not really know where we are going (we just know where we do not want to be). We do not know what a just world looks like, feels like, tastes like, sounds like. Therefore, the goal, at this point, is not to fix it or reaffirm how you will go about fixing it. The goal is to be willing and committed to be a part of making it. >(Akinleye Adesola, 2020)

educated, speculative questions, formulated with the head, with its quotations and bibliography, but questions from the guts, formulated with the feet, risking the type> (Férrandez-Savater Amador, 2023).

Desert zombie-images. Desert zombie-practices. Desert the well-known history. Desert the same old questions. Desert what names itself as established. Desert the always-same-directional flow of value, of attention-ings. Sense the moment of variability and its potentialities never-already-determined. Desert promises. Desert modern promises. Desert colonial promises. Distrust and desert. Desert as an improvisational score. Desert together. Desert in friendship, in alliances.

Take a moment to nap and sense which ghosts are haunting your sleep.

Tables – 23 diciembre 2021-28 junio 2023

A photo of our living-room table: That the living-room table appears and not another kind of table, might reveal something about the ‘orientation’ of our essay (misquoting from Sarah Ahmed’s ‘Queer Phenomenology’). Escrituras desde mesas de living, de tés compartidos, de charlas y excitaciones. De deslengües bífidos que intentan escribirse conjuntos. Escribires digestivos y residuales.

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